

Initialization Methods Lower Energy Needs of Spiking Neural Networks for Land Cover Classification

Roberta Pärna¹, Dylan Adams², Ashiq Anjum³, Magdalena Zajackowska², Rajesh Sharma¹, Shirin Dora^{*2}

¹*Institute of Computer Science, University of Tartu, Estonia*

²*Department of Computer Science, Loughborough University, United Kingdom*

³*School of Computing and Mathematic Sciences, University of Leicester, United Kingdom*

Spiking Neural Networks (SNN) have received a lot of attention as an energy-efficient alternative to Artificial Neural Networks (ANN). They are particularly useful for machine learning applications in space. Many learning algorithms have been developed to build energy-efficient SNNs and applied to address real-world problems. However, the impact of initialization choices on the energy-efficiency of SNNs has not been investigated thoroughly. In this paper, we study the impact of initial values for neuronal time constants and weights, and the reset mechanisms for membrane potential of neurons on the energy requirements of trained SNNs. For this purpose, we trained several SNNs with different initialization choices on the land cover classification problem using the EuroSAT dataset. It could be clearly observed that lower initial weights and higher initial neuronal time constants result in SNNs that generate fewer spikes without exhibiting any loss in performance. Different resetting mechanisms did not have a significant impact on the number of spikes generated by trained SNNs.

1 Introduction

Advances in training accurate Artificial Neural Networks (ANN) over the last decade have led to development of autonomous solutions in a broad range of sectors like agriculture [1], manufacturing [2] and even space [3, 4]. Training and using ANNs for inference requires use of energy intensive devices like graphical processing units. In terrestrial applications, high energy requirements of ANNs can be handled by replenishing existing energy sources or using alternative energy sources. However, the aforementioned solutions are unsuitable for applications of machine learning in space. An excessive burden on the limited energy budgets of devices in space undermines their capabilities and possibly, their lifetime.

Spiking Neural Networks (SNN) have been widely recognized as an energy-efficient alternative to ANNs.

SNNs consist of spiking neurons which transmit and receive information in the form of events, called spikes, at precise time instants. Different from ANNs where neurons are always active, the binary and sparse nature of spikes make SNNs an inherently energy-efficient computational paradigm.

The energy-efficient characteristics of SNNs have been exploited for various applications involving non-terrestrial datasets. The limited energy budgets of satellites has motivated the use of SNNs for problems involving earth observation datasets like land cover classification [5] and weather classification [6]. These methods rely on the inherent energy-efficient characteristics of SNNs for applications that require low-power compute.

A recent work focused on improving the energy requirements of SNNs built by converting trained ANNs for the land cover classification problem [7]. The converted SNNs are fine-tuned to reduce their energy requirements by lowering the firing rate of neurons and the length of simulation. Besides above-mentioned applications, there are many algorithms to build energy-efficient SNNs developed using benchmark datasets which are discussed in Section 2. However, existing research has not studied the impact of initialization strategies on the energy requirements of trained SNNs.

In this paper, the impact of using various initialization strategies on the energy requirements of trained SNNs is studied. In particular, we focus on initialization mechanisms for time constants of Leaky Integrate and Fire (LIF) neurons and weights, and strategies for resetting the membrane potential of neurons. For this purpose, several SNNs with different initialization choices are trained for the land cover classification problem using the EuroSAT dataset [8]. It is observed that higher neuronal time constants and lower initial weights resulted in networks that generated fewer spikes without a significant loss in classifica-

*Corresponding author. E-Mail: s.dora@lboro.ac.uk

tion accuracy. Resetting mechanisms did not have a significant impact on the number of spikes generated by the trained networks.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. Section 2 presents the related works. Section 3 describe the methods used to build SNNs. Section 4 reports the results of experiments and Section 5 presents a discussion on the results from this study.

2 Related Works

In this section, a review of existing research on energy-efficient SNNs is presented.

The discontinuity at the time of spike has led to development of many learning algorithms for training SNNs [9–11]. A detailed survey on error-backpropagation based methods for training SNNs has been presented in [12]. The goal of building energy-efficient SNNs has only started attracting attention recently.

Early works in this direction focused on adapting techniques developed for ANNs to SNNs like quantization and pruning. In a quantized network, the neuronal activations and weights can only have a discrete set of values resulting in lower energy needs for computations in the network. This approach has been used by applying quantization-aware training to CNNs and then converting it to an SNN [13].

Pruning involves removing connections from the network without impacting the performance of the network significantly. In [14], energy-efficient SNNs are developed by pruning connections based on the differences between output spike trains generated by the network. A combination of quantization and pruning has also been used to build SNNs with lower computational requirements [15]. In [16], connection- and neuron-level pruning have been combined to obtain energy-efficient SNNs. Another direction of research has focused on lowering energy needs of SNNs through modified loss functions.

An activity-based penalty term has been proposed for building SNNs that generate fewer spikes during inference [17]. The penalty term discourages higher number of spikes in each layer and the whole network. AutoSNN [18] proposes an adaptation of neural architecture search to build energy-efficient SNNs.

The above-mentioned methods have focused on building energy-efficient SNNs through application of techniques like quantization, pruning and learning algorithms that penalizes models with higher energy requirements. In this paper, we focus on understanding the impact of initialization strategies on the energy requirements of trained SNNs.

3 Method

In this section, the network architecture and the learning algorithm used in this paper are presented.

3.1 Architecture

All networks consist of $L \in \mathbb{N}^+$ fully connected layers, with each layer $l \in \{1, \dots, L\}$ containing $N^{(l)}$ spiking neurons. Neurons are modelled as the Leaky Integrate and Fire (LIF) neurons [19]. Incoming spikes at time $t \in \{0, \dots, T\}$ are integrated into the membrane potential of the LIF neurons. Here T represents the duration of simulation. $v_j^{(l)}(t) \in \mathbb{R}$ denotes the membrane potential of neuron j in layer l at time step t , given as

$$v_j^{(l)}(t) = \beta_j^{(l)} v_j^{(l)}(t-1) + \sum_i w_{ij}^{(l-1)} s_i^{(l-1)}(t) \quad (1)$$

where $\beta_j^{(l)}$ represents the time constant of the neuron j in layer l . $w_{ij}^{(l-1)}$ represent the weight of the connection between neurons i in layer $(l-1)$ and j in layer l . $s_i^{(l-1)}(t)$ represents the spike function, given by

$$s_i^{(l-1)} = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } v_i^{(l-1)} \geq \theta_i^{(l-1)}, \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

where θ denotes the threshold of the neuron. The threshold are initialized to 1 and are learnt during training.

Each spikes results in a reset of a neuron's membrane potential. In this paper, we study two different strategies to apply the reset, namely Reset to Constant (RtC) and Reset by Subtraction (RbS). RtC sets the membrane potential of a neuron to zero after a spike and RbS reduces the membrane potential by a value equal to the threshold of the neuron.

The predicted classes are determined based on the output neuron that generates largest number of spikes.

3.2 Learning Algorithm

The weights, time constants and thresholds of all neurons in the network are updated using error-backpropagation for SNNs. Cross entropy loss based on the count of spikes is used as a loss function to train the networks. The shifted arc-tan function [20] is used as a surrogate for the derivative of the spike function with respect to the membrane potential of a neuron, given as

$$\frac{ds_i^{(l)}(t)}{dv_i^{(l)}(t)} \approx \frac{1}{\pi} \times \frac{1}{1 + (\pi v_i^{(l)}(t))^2} \quad (3)$$

4 Results

In this section, the results of performance evaluation and energy requirements of SNNs initialized using different strategies are presented¹. Specifically, we study the impact of using different initialization techniques for neuronal time constants and weights, and resetting mechanisms for membrane potential of neurons.

All SNNs in this paper are trained on the land cover classification problem using the RGB version of the EuroSAT dataset [21]. The dataset consists of 27000 samples. 90% of the dataset is used for training and 10% of the samples are reserved for testing. Each samples in the EuroSAT dataset is processed by a ResNet-18 architecture which is trained using the Seasonal Contrast (SeCo) [5] unsupervised training method. The ResNet-18 architectures provides a 512 dimensional feature representation for each sample which are presented to the SNNs. Each sample is converted into spikes using rate coding with a simulation duration of 20 milliseconds. The precise time of spikes are determined using a binomial distribution with mean equal to the value of a feature.

The performance of the trained SNNs is estimated using overall classification accuracy which is computed as percentage of samples that are correctly classified. The energy requirements of the trained SNNs is measured in terms of the average number of spikes ($\eta^{(l)}$) generated by neurons in layer l of the trained networks, given by

$$\eta^{(l)} = \frac{\sum_{i,t} s_i^{(l)}(t)}{N^{(l)}} \quad (4)$$

where $N^{(l)}$ represents the number of neurons in layer l of the network. Using average number of spikes, rather than total number of spikes, enables a comparison irrespective of the number of neurons in the network.

All the SNNs used in this paper have three hidden layers with 1028, 2048 and 1028 LIF neurons, respectively. The neuronal time constants and thresholds for all neurons are also learned using stochastic gradient descent for SNNs. The models are trained for 100 epochs using the Adam optimizer with a learning rate of $1e-5$ and a minibatch size of 16. The weights for all SNNs are initialized using the normal distribution $\mathcal{N}(\mu, \sigma)$ with σ in all SNNs set to 0.1. The impact of weight initialization on the number of spikes is studied for two different values of μ , namely -0.01 and 0.01.

¹The code for all experiments reported in this paper will be made available at <https://github.com/robertaparna/snn-transfer-learning>.

Figure 1: Average number of spikes in each layer of the network with different weight initialization mechanisms.

The neuronal time constants for all LIF neurons are randomly initialized from the uniform distribution $[\beta_{min}, \beta_{max}]$. The impact of initial values of neuronal time constants is studied for three different regimes, namely low, medium and high. The values of neuronal time constants for the three regimes are initialized in the intervals $[0, 0.34]$, $[0.34, 0.67]$ and $[0.67, 1.0]$, respectively. The impact of reset mechanism on the number of spikes generated in the network is studied for two different strategies, RtC and RbS. All results reported in this paper are based of 5 repetition of each experimental condition.

Mean Weight	Accuracy (%)	Average number of spikes (layer-wise)
-0.01	84.6 (0.003)	1.2, 0.7, 0.5, 3.5 (0.07), (0.04), (0.08), (0.3)
0.01	85.04 (0.006)	6.9, 16.3, 19.6, 4.8 (0.13), (0.12), (0.07), (0.14)

Table 1: Performance and number of spikes generated for SNNs with different weight initialization strategies.

4.1 Impact of initial weights

Table 1 shows the performance and number of spikes generated by SNNs when weights are initialized using normal distributions with mean -0.01 and 0.01, respectively. The number in parentheses represent the standard deviation across 5 different runs of the same experiment. It can be observed that the networks with different strategies for initialization of weight have similar classification accuracy.

Figure 1 shows the average number of spikes in each layer of the networks with two different initial mean value of weights. The networks initialized using value of -0.01 for μ have lower average spike counts in all layer of the network after training. The average spike counts for all layers are separately compared using the paired t-test. The null hypothesis is that the average spikes counts obtained using the two strategies are not significantly different. This null hypothesis is rejected for all layers at 99% confidence interval.

It may also be noted from Figure 1 that the networks with lower initial weights exhibited a reduction in the number of spikes from first to third hidden layer in the network. In contrast, the networks with higher initial weights exhibited an increase in the number of spikes from first to third hidden layer. The significant change in the number of spikes from third hidden layer to the output layer for both types of networks could be attributed to the stronger influence of the loss function on the output layer.

Beta Range	Accuracy (%)	Average number of spikes (layer-wise)
Low	85.8 (0.010)	4.9, 5.2, 2.5, 3.9 (0.07), (0.09), (0.06), (0.10)
Medium	87.0 (0.011)	3.5, 3.3, 2.2, 3.6 (0.10), (0.05), (0.11), (0.03)
High	88.0 (0.004)	1.3, 0.6, 1.1, 2.8 (0.04), (0.04), (0.04), (0.16)

Table 2: Performance and number of spikes generated for SNNs with different beta initialization strategies.

4.2 Impact of initial neuronal time constants

Table 2 shows the performance and number of spikes generated by SNNs with different initial values for neuronal time constants. Specifically, neuronal time constants are initialized using uniform distributions with low [0, 0.34], medium [0.34, 0.67] and high [0.67, 1.0] ranges.

The average number of spikes in all layers of the network decreased with an increase in the initial values of the neuronal time constants. Paired t-test is used to compare the average number of spikes for high range with low and medium ranges, respectively for initial values of neuronal time constants. The average number of spikes for all layers are compared separately. The null hypothesis is that average number of spikes for high range is not different from those of the other

Reset Method	Accuracy (%)	Average number of spikes (layer-wise)
RtC	86.8 (0.006)	2.4, 1.6, 1.7, 2.1 (0.14), (0.08), (0.13), (0.16)
RbS	86.5 (0.009)	2.2, 1.8, 2.0, 3.0 (0.23), (0.12), (0.13), (0.50)

Table 3: Performance and number of spikes generated for SNNs with different reset mechanisms.

ranges of neuronal time constants. The p-values obtained indicated that the average number of spikes for high range are lower than the other ranges of neuronal time constants in all layers of trained networks at a confidence interval of 99%.

4.3 Impact of resetting mechanisms

Table 3 shows the performance and number of spikes generated by SNNs when the thresholds of the neurons are reset using the RtC and RbS strategies, respectively. The classification accuracy and the average number of spikes in the the networks with RtC and RbS strategies for reset are similar.

The average number of spikes in the networks with two reset mechanisms are compared using the paired t-test. The null hypothesis is that the two reset strategies result in networks with similar average number of spikes. This hypothesis is not rejected for any of the layer at 99% confidence interval indicating that reset mechanisms do not have a significant impact on the number of spikes generated in the network. At 95% confidence interval, the null hypothesis is rejected only for the output layer.

5 Discussion

In this paper, we have studied the impact of initial weights and neuronal time constants, and the resetting mechanisms for membrane potential of neurons on the energy requirements and performance of the trained SNNs. For this purpose, we trained several SNNs with different initialization hyperparameters on the land cover classification problem using the EuroSAT dataset. It was observed that networks with lower initial weights and higher neuronal time constants generated fewer spikes without a significant loss in performance while resetting methods did not impact number of spikes significantly.

The results reported in this paper clearly highlight that initialization strategies used for SNNs have a sig-

nificant impact on the energy required by the trained SNNs. Our future work will focus on expanding the scope of hyperparameters studied and identifying combinations of appropriate initialization strategies to further optimize the number of spikes generated in the trained SNNs. Additionally, consideration of other factors like number of neurons, precision of weights and neuronal states will also influence the energy requirements of neuromorphic hardware. Further work on understanding the impact of various initialization strategies on SNNs should aim to develop a comprehensive understanding based on the different factors highlighted above.

References

- Saleem, M. H., Potgieter, J. & Arif, K. M. Automation in agriculture by machine and deep learning techniques: A review of recent developments. *Precision Agriculture* **22**, 2053–2091 (2021).
- Tercan, H. & Meisen, T. Machine learning and deep learning based predictive quality in manufacturing: a systematic review. *Journal of Intelligent Manufacturing* **33**, 1879–1905 (2022).
- Zheng, G., Li, X., Zhang, R.-H. & Liu, B. Purely satellite data-driven deep learning forecast of complicated tropical instability waves. *Science advances* **6**, eaba1482 (2020).
- Yeh, C. *et al.* Using publicly available satellite imagery and deep learning to understand economic well-being in Africa. *Nature communications* **11**, 2583 (2020).
- Mañas, O., Lacoste, A., Giró-i-Nieto, X., Vázquez, D. & Rodríguez, P. Seasonal Contrast: Unsupervised Pre-Training from Uncurated Remote Sensing Data. *CoRR* **abs/2103.16607**. arXiv: 2103.16607. <https://arxiv.org/abs/2103.16607> (2021).
- Toğaçar, M., Ergen, B. & Cömert, Z. Detection of weather images by using spiking neural networks of deep learning models. *Neural Computing and Applications* **33**, 6147–6159 (2021).
- Kucik, A. S. & Meoni, G. *Investigating spiking neural networks for energy-efficient on-board ai applications. a case study in land cover and land use classification in Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition* (2021), 2020–2030.
- Helber, P., Bischke, B., Dengel, A. & Borth, D. Eurosat: A novel dataset and deep learning benchmark for land use and land cover classification. *IEEE Journal of Selected Topics in Applied Earth Observations and Remote Sensing* **12**, 2217–2226 (2019).
- Bohte, S. M., Kok, J. N. & La Poutré, H. Error-backpropagation in temporally encoded networks of spiking neurons. *en. Neurocomputing* **48**, 17–37. issn: 0925-2312. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0925231201006580> (2023) (Oct. 2002).
- Shrestha, S. B. & Orchard, G. *SLAYER: Spike Layer Error Re-assignment in Time in Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems* **31** (Curran Associates, Inc., 2018). https://papers.nips.cc/paper_files/paper/2018/hash/82f2b308c3b01637c607ce05f52a2fed-Abstract.html (2023).
- Zhang, W. & Li, P. *Temporal Spike Sequence Learning via Backpropagation for Deep Spiking Neural Networks in Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems* **33** (Curran Associates, Inc., 2020), 12022–12033. <https://proceedings.neurips.cc/paper/2020/hash/8bdb5058376143fa358981954e7626b8-Abstract.html> (2024).
- Dampfhofer, M., Mesquida, T., Valentian, A. & Anghel, L. Backpropagation-based learning techniques for deep spiking neural networks: A survey. *IEEE Transactions on Neural Networks and Learning Systems* (2023).
- Sorbaro, M., Liu, Q., Bortone, M. & Sheik, S. *Optimizing the energy consumption of spiking neural networks for neuromorphic applications* 2020. arXiv: 1912.01268 [cs.NE].
- Wu, D., Lin, X. & Du, P. *An adaptive structure learning algorithm for multi-layer spiking neural networks in 2019 15th International Conference on Computational Intelligence and Security (CIS)* (2019), 98–102.
- Rathi, N., Panda, P. & Roy, K. STDP-based pruning of connections and weight quantization in spiking neural networks for energy-efficient recognition. *IEEE Transactions on Computer-Aided Design of Integrated Circuits and Systems* **38**, 668–677 (2018).
- Shi, X., Ding, J., Hao, Z. & Yu, Z. *Towards Energy Efficient Spiking Neural Networks: An Unstructured Pruning Framework in The Twelfth International Conference on Learning Representations* (2023).
- Suetake, K., Ushimaru, T., Saiin, R. & Sawada, Y. Spiking Synaptic Penalty: Appropriate Penalty Term for Energy-Efficient Spiking Neural Networks. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2302.01500* (2023).
- Na, B. *et al.* *Autosnn: Towards energy-efficient spiking neural networks in International Conference on Machine Learning* (2022), 16253–16269.
- Gerstner, W. & Kistler, W. M. *Spiking neuron models: Single neurons, populations, plasticity* (Cambridge university press, 2002).
- Neftci, E. O., Mostafa, H. & Zenke, F. Surrogate gradient learning in spiking neural networks: Bringing the power of gradient-based optimization to spiking neural networks. *IEEE Signal Processing Magazine* **36**, 51–63 (2019).
- Helber, P., Bischke, B., Dengel, A. & Borth, D. *Introducing EuroSAT: A Novel Dataset and Deep Learning Benchmark for Land Use and Land Cover Classification in IGARSS 2018-2018 IEEE International Geoscience and Remote Sensing Symposium* (2018), 204–207.